

Fostering Engagement through a Latency-Optimized LLM-based Dialogue System for Multimodal ECA Responses

Supplemental Material

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Index Terms—large language model, embodied conversational agents, latency, multi-modal responses, wizard-of-oz, virtual reality

We have a supplemental video showing our system in action at: <https://youtu.be/Sc9PhKmNpBE>.

I. IMPLEMENTATION IN UNREAL 5.3

Fig. 1: A high-level class diagram outlining how the main components of the LLM-driven dialogue system were implemented in Unreal Engine 5.3. The components either belong to an ECA actor or the user. On the user actor, the speech input is located. On the agent actor, the input receiver, the decision-making, the mind and Output, are located — mimicking the flow of information.

This section features a short overview over how the Large Language Model (LLM)-driven dialogue system was implemented in Unreal Engine 5.3. Fig. 1 shows a high-level class diagram of the main components. Only important properties and methods are listed for the main dialogue system. The class

diagram does not show any classes that were implemented for controlling the user study. The class diagram also indicates the *GameMode* class which is used, among other things, for debugging commands which are sent to all *Receivers* in the scene. The implementation was done mostly in C++ and specific adjustments, for example for different agents, in Blueprints. The classes, except *struct* and *enum* types, are so-called ActorComponents within Unreal Engine, meaning they are attached to an owning actor such as the Embodied Conversational Agent (ECA) or the user. Multiple instances of these components might exist in an environment if multiple agents are present.

Dashed lines in the class diagram indicate that a component forwards information to another component. For example, in the main pipeline of the dialogue system, the *Input* component receives a stimulus, either by the user speaking or by an external trigger, then forwards this to the *DecisionMaking*, which forwards its decision to the *MindComponent* and the *Output*.

As indicated by the boxes for user and ECA, the abstract class *Sender* is used by the users *SpeechInput* and the *TTSOutput* of the ECA, meaning there is technically no difference in an agent being triggered by the user talking or by another agent talking. Some components feature multiple implementations which are, for example, used for debugging and testing purposes. In general, the system does not need to be powered by an LLM, as the *DecisionMaking* could also be implemented differently.

Concerning the speech streaming feature, this feature cannot be used via the REST Application Programming Interface (API) and no official C/C++ library was available, the Java library was used as part of the backend, which was also used for controlling the study and collecting metrics. As with all communication between this Java backend and the Unreal application, the intermediate audio data was also transferred using REST.

II. SERVICE SELECTION

This section covers the toughs behind selecting the cloud services we selected for our LLM pipeline.

During the implementation, the cloud Speech-to-Text (STT) services by Google Cloud and OpenAI were tested, alongside the local versions of the Whisper¹ models by OpenAI. The Google Cloud service has support streaming the input audio² to lower the latency between the user fishing to talk and the text to be ready. Additionally, it has also support for supplying metadata to improve the recognition quality. Because of the additional features, the STT service by Google Cloud was chosen for the implementation. Another advantage of the Google Cloud STT when looking at the pricing is that new customers receive \$300 free credits and 60 minutes free transcription per month³. Regarding streaming the input, in the implementation, the audio was captured with a sample rate of 48 kHz and sent to the service in increments of 30000 samples, which is about 0.63 seconds of audio. In the sending process, these samples were down-sampled to 16 kHz for faster processing.

During the implementation of this system, the following LLM models were tested: Llama 3.0 (8B), Llama 3.0 (70B) and Llama 3.1 (8B) from the Llama⁴ family by Meta⁵, GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4, GPT-4 Turbo, GPT-4o Mini and GPT-4 from the Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT) family by OpenAI⁶ and Claude 3 Haiku, Claude 3 Opus, Claude 3 Sonnet and Claude 3.5 Sonnet from the Claude family by Anthropic⁷. In general, the Llama models had the advantage of being able to run locally and not being tied to a cloud service. However, they were unable to respond in the defined JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format. The GPT and Claude models both returned good results in quality, giving good responses for the tested situations in the desired JSON format, utilizing all fields and abilities available to them. During testing, slightly higher quality in the responses by the GPT models was observed compared to the Claude models, especially in situations, where information was missing, for example, because the STT service misunderstood a critical word. Within a family, a progression in quality was observed towards the newer models.

For the TTS, Amazon Polly⁸, Google's Cloud Text-to-Speech service⁹ and the Text-to-Speech (TTS) service by OpenAI¹⁰ were tested. The quality between these services is comparable, the services by Amazon and Google offer more voices compared to OpenAI. All services were configured to output as Pulse-Code Modulation (PCM) as this was the fastest option across all services as it has no overhead through file

¹<https://github.com/openai/whisper>

²<https://cloud.google.com/STT/docs/transcribe-streaming-audio>

³<https://cloud.google.com/STT/?hl=en#pricing>

⁴<https://www.llama.com>

⁵<https://about.meta.com>

⁶<https://openai.com/>

⁷<https://www.anthropic.com/>

⁸<https://aws.amazon.com/polly>

⁹<https://cloud.google.com/text-to-speech>

¹⁰<https://platform.openai.com/docs/guides/speech-to-text>

Fig. 2: The three embodiments used in the study. From left to right: A woman, a woman in a driving TV mimicking a video call, and a driving robot. Each of them is wearing a different symbol used to identify the different conditions in the user study.

headers, as would be the case with, for example, the WAV or MP3 format. To measure the performance, the services were directly compared in their performance with the sentence 'Hello, welcome to our museum! How can I help you?', with $N = 30$ samples, resulting in a time of 0.224 ± 0.116 s for Polly, 0.404 ± 0.181 s for Google Cloud, and 0.981 ± 0.205 s for OpenAI. In the implementation, Amazon Polly was used, as it achieved the fastest generation times during testing and in comparison to related work. Another advantage of using Amazon Polly is that similar to the speech recognition service by Google, the so-called *AWS Free Tier* grants five million characters for free per month for a total of 12 months. During the development and the user study, a total of about 235000 characters were used over a time of about seven months, which is far away from the limit. The *neural* engine was used with the *Joanna* voice, which is a female US-English-speaking voice.

III. OTHER EMBODIMENTS

This section gives an overview over all embodiments used in our user study, as in the main paper, we mainly report the results for the MetaHuman embodiment.

We employed three different embodiment, seen in Fig. 2, as the museums guide. The first one, the female MetaHuman ($E_{MetaHuman}$), has already been discussed in-depth in the main paper. The second embodiment, E_{Remote} , simulates telepresence by displaying the same MetaHuman during a remote video call on a mobile robot. Finally, E_{Robot} is a mix of the telepresence display and the character Wheatley from Portal 2¹¹ and represents a moving robot as an entirely robotic system. All embodiments utilized the US-English voice *Joanna* from Amazon Polly. While the $E_{MetaHuman}$ utilizes facial expressions, gestures, and attention, E_{Remote} only

¹¹https://store.steampowered.com/app/620/Portal_2

shows facial expressions, and E_{Robot} neither. All embodiments can use the *move_to* field.

In the study, six different symbols were used to later identify the conditions in the end questionnaire: *Star*, *Flower*, *Tower*, *House*, *Sun*, and *Windmill*. Three of the symbols and how they were worn by the different embodiments can be seen in Fig. 2.

IV. QUESTIONNAIRES

In this section the complete questionnaires used after every condition and at the end of the study are displayed. All questionnaires were conducted via SoSciSurvey¹².

A. Interim Questionnaire

This section lists the complete interim questionnaire.

- 1) StudyID which the participant randomly picked at the start of the study.
- 2) Social Presence (SP) from the Multimodal Presence Scale for Virtual Reality Environments (MPS) by [1] *5-point Likert Scale (1=completely disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neither disagree nor agree, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree)*
 - **SP1** I felt like I was in the presence of a living museum guide in the virtual environment.
 - **SP2** I felt that the museum guide in the virtual environment was aware of my presence.
 - **SP3** The museum guide in the virtual environment appeared to be sentient (conscious and alive) to me.
 - **SP4** During the simulation there were times where the computer interfaces seemed to disappear, and I felt like I was working directly with the museum guide.
 - **SP5** I had a sense that I was interacting with a museum guide in the virtual environment, rather than a computer simulation.
- 3) Godspeed I: Anthropomorphism (ANT) by [2] *5-point bipolar Likert Scale 1 to 5*
 - **ANT 1** Fake - Natural
 - **ANT 2** Machinelike - Humanlike
 - **ANT 3** Unconscious - Conscious
 - **ANT 4** Artificial - Lifelike
 - **ANT 5** Moving rigidly - Moving elegantly
- 4) Selection of questions from the Artificial-Social-Agent Questionnaire (ASAQ) by [3] *7-point rating scale [-3, ..., 3], -3=disagree, 0=neither agree nor disagree, 3=agree*
 - **NB2** The museum guide acts naturally.
 - **PF1** The museum guide does its task well.
 - **PF2** The museum guide does not hinder me.
 - **PF3** I am capable of succeeding with the museum guide.
 - **UT1** The museum guide always gives good advice.
 - **UT2** The museum guide acts truthfully.
 - **UT3** I can rely on the museum guide.
 - **AC4** The museum guide appears confused. [Reversed]
- 5) Godspeed IV: Perceived Intelligence (PI) by [2] *5-point bipolar Likert Scale 1 to 5*
 - **PI 1** Incompetent - Competent
 - **PI 2** Ignorant - Knowledgeable
 - **PI 3** Irresponsible - Responsible
 - **PI 4** Unintelligent - Intelligent
 - **PI 5** Foolish - Sensible
- 6) Custom questions rating the responses by the agent *7-point bipolar Likert Scale 1 to 7* 'The responses by the guide...'
 - came too slow - came too fast
 - were too vague - were too precise
 - were too short - were too long
 - were spoken too slow - were spoken too fast
- 7) Selection of questions from the Chatbot Usability Scale by [4] *5-point Likert Scale (1=completely disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neither disagree nor agree, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree)*
 - **8.1.1** I felt that my intentions were understood by the museum guide.
 - **8.1.2** The museum guide was able to guide me to my goal.
 - **8.1.3** I find that the museum guide understands what I want and helps me achieve my goal.
 - **9.1.1** The museum guide gave relevant information during the whole conversation.
 - **9.1.2** The museum guide is good at providing me with a helpful response at any point of the process.
 - **9.1.3** The museum guide provided relevant information as and when I needed it.
 - **12.1.1** I found the museum guide's responses clear.
 - **12.1.2** The museum guide only states understandable answers.
 - **12.1.3** The museum guide's responses were easy to understand.
- 8) Custom questions rating the difficulty for every of the three experienced tasks in this condition. *5-point Likert Scale (1=very easy, 2=easy, 3=normal, 4=hard, 5=very hard)*
 - *Task 1* (E.g. How many birds are in the painting 'The Therapist'?)
 - *Task 2* (E.g. Where is the shop located?)
 - *Task 3* (E.g. On which hill does the Mona Lisa stand?)
- 9) Custom questions rating the perceived helpfulness of the agent for every of the three experienced tasks in this condition. *5-point Likert Scale (1=Not helpful at all, 5=very helpful)*
 - *Task 1* (E.g. How many birds are in the painting 'The Therapist'?)
 - *Task 2* (E.g. Where is the shop located?)
 - *Task 3* (E.g. On which hill does the Mona Lisa stand?)
- 10) For condition 2 (Flower) to 6 (Windmill), custom questions comparing the agent presented to the participant in

¹²<https://www.sosicisurvey.de>

the last condition to the current condition.

5-point bipolar Likert Scale

- I felt a stronger social connection to **the last** museum guide - I felt a stronger social connection to **the current** museum guide
- I preferred teaming up with **the last** museum guide for solving my tasks - I preferred teaming up with **the current** museum guide for solving my tasks
- I was able to fulfill the tasks better with **the last** museum guide - I was able to fulfill the tasks better with **the current** museum guide
- I preferred the conversation dynamics with **the last** museum guide - I preferred the conversation dynamics with **the current** museum guide
- The conversation with **the last** guide felt more natural - The conversation with **the current** guide felt more natural
- I felt more trust towards **the last** museum guide - I felt more trust towards **the current** museum guide
- I think **the last** museum guide was more trustworthy - I think **the current** museum guide was more trustworthy
- I think **the last** museum guide was more competent - I think **the current** museum guide was more competent

B. End Questionnaire

This section lists all questions from the end questionnaire. All section based questions were single-choice, if not stated otherwise.

- 1) StudyID which the participant randomly picked at the start of the study.
- 2) Ranking of the six conditions by dragging cards with the condition name on them together with a textual explanation why they chose the ranking. These rankings were in terms of...
 - The trust the participant felt towards the agent.
 - The difficulty of the tasks.
 - How natural and comfortable the museum guide and the interactions with them felt to the participant.
 - How competent the museum guide felt to the participant.
- 3) Single choice of the condition which museum guide the participant would like to see again the most together with a textual explanation.
- 4) Free text question about what the participant liked about the presented agents.
- 5) Free text question about what the participant disliked about the presented agents.
- 6) Free text question about the study and organization.
- 7) Free text question what participants think how the presented museum guides differed other than in their appearance.
- 8) It is explained that some of the characters were controlled by an LLM and some by a human (WoZ). The participants were then asked to decide for every condition whether

they think they were controlled by an LLM or a human which they could further explain in a free-text question.

- 1) Gender selectable from *Male, Female, Non-binary* and *Self-described* with a free-text field.
- 2) Age in years.
- 3) Dominant hand selectable from *Right hand, Left hand* and *Ambidextrous*.
- 4) Vision selectable from the following statements:
 - I have normal vision.
 - I have corrected vision (glasses / contact lenses).
 - Not corrected defective vision: [Free text].
- 5) How often the participant used a VR system before, selectable from *0, 1, 2-10, 11-50, 50+*.
- 6) Whether they have used ChatGPT by OpenAI or comparable LLMs before, by selecting one of the following statements:
 - I have never used ChatGPT (or similar AI language models).
 - I have used ChatGPT (or similar AI language models), but I am not using it on a regular basis.
 - I am using ChatGPT (or similar AI language models) regularly but not more than a few times per week.
 - I am using ChatGPT (or similar AI language models) daily.
- 7) Whether they have experience with ECAs, by selecting one or multiple of the following statements:
 - I have no experience with ECAs.
 - I have worked with ECAs in an academic context.
 - I have designed or programmed ECAs myself.
 - I have knowledge about LLM-driven ECAs.
 - I have encountered ECAs in Virtual Reality applications.
- 8) Whether they have experience with NPCs, by selecting one or multiple of the following statements:
 - I have no experience with NPCs.
 - I have encountered NPCs (e.g., in video games).
 - I have encountered NPCs in Virtual Reality (VR).
 - I have encountered NPCs in Augmented Reality (AR).
 - I had conversations with NPCs through multiple choice dialogues.
 - I had conversations with NPC through natural language (both spoken or written).
- 9) Whether they know ChatGPT would play a role in the study before attending, by selecting one of the following statements:
 - I did not know it at all.
 - I thought so, but did not know it.
 - I knew it at some time, but was not aware of it in the study.
 - I knew it before and was aware of it during the study.

V. LLM PROMPT EXAMPLE

This section holds an example for an LLM prompt, similar to situations in the user study. In this context, the user said

'Hello, can you help me?' to the ECA (embodied as the MetaHuman). [S] stands for the system role and [U] for the user role. This prompt especially shows, how multimodal controls are embedded into the LLM prompt (see Line 3). The LLM does not answer with empty fields, therefore in this example, there is no `move_to` field.

```
[S] The user is on a scavenger hunt through the museum. You insist on leading the user to paintings they have questions about and do not answer specific questions when you are not at the painting. You only start going to the painting if specifically requested by the user. You and the user are the only persons in the museum. Only the paintings which are available as waypoints do exist, there are also only paintings and no other art pieces in the museum. You can also answer any other questions the user has, if you know the answer.
[S] Your name is Vivian. You work in a virtual museum
[S] You output a json with the following format, all fields marked with '?' are optional: {response: string, face: 'neutral' | 'happiness' | 'sadness' | 'surprise' | 'fear' | 'anger' | 'disgust' | 'contempt' | 'slight_smile', gesture: 'none' | 'wave' | 'talk', attention: 'user' | 'user_and_target', move_to?: string}
[S] You use the 'user_and_target' attention when talking with the user about a waypoint. You can move to the following waypoints using the move_to field. You can move to waypoint if you are already there. This is useful to reposition yourself, if you are blocking the view of the user.
[S] Waypoint timeless_hall: Name = Timeless Hall
[S] Waypoint modern_nature_gallery: Name = Modern Nature Gallery
[S] Waypoint self-portrait_on_the_6th_wedding_anniversary: Name = Self-Portrait on the 6th Wedding Anniversary, Description = Painted by Paula Modersohn-Becker in 1906. Inside the Chamber of Self-Discovery
[S] Waypoint self-portrait_with_model: Name = Self-Portrait with Model, Description = Painted by Ernst Ludwig Kirchner in 1910. Inside the Chamber of Self-Discovery
[S] Waypoint self-portrait_in_black: Name = Self-Portrait in Black, Description = Painted by Max Beckmann in 1944. Inside the Chamber of Self-Discovery
[S] Waypoint coastal_landscape: Name = Coastal Landscape, Description = Painted by Edvard Munch in 1918. Inside the Modern Nature Gallery
[S] Waypoint winter_landscape_in_moonlight: Name = Winter Landscape in Moonlight, Description = Painted by Ernst Ludwig Kirchner in 1919. Inside the Modern Nature Gallery
[S] Waypoint the_temptation_of_saint_antonius: Name = The Temptation of Saint Antonius, Description = Painted by Max Ernst in 1945. Inside the Vision Wing
[S] Waypoint the_oxbow: Name = The Oxbow, Description = Painted by Thomas Coloe in 1836. Inside the Modern Nature Gallery
[S] Waypoint the_persistence_of_memory: Name = The Persistence of Memory, Description = Painted by Salvador Dali in 1931. Inside the Vision Wing
[S] Waypoint the_therapist: Name = The Therapist, Description = Painted by Rene Megritte in 1937. Inside the Vision Wing
[S] Waypoint guide_stand: Name = Guide Stand, Description = Your stand
```

```
[S] Waypoint vision_wing: Name = Vision Wing, Description = Contains surreal paintings
[S] Waypoint mosaic_hall: Name = Mosaic Hall, Description = Currently has no paintings
[S] Waypoint chamber_of_self-discovery: Name = Chamber of Self-Discovery, Description = Has the three self-portraits in this museum
[S] Waypoint mona_lisa: Name = Mona Lisa, Description = Inside the Timeless Hall
[S] Waypoint wanderer_above_the_sea_of_fog: Name = Wanderer above the Sea of Fog, Description = Painted by Caspar David Friedrich in 1818. Inside the Timeless Hall. The oldest painting in the museum.
[S] Waypoint the_starry_night: Name = The Starry Night, Description = Painted by Vincent van Gogh in 1889. Inside the Timeless Hall
[S] Waypoint water_lilies: Name = Water Lilies, Description = Painted by Claude Monet in 1906. Inside the Timeless Hall
[S] Waypoint the_weeping_woman: Name = The Weeping Woman, Description = By Pablo Picasso in 1937. Inside the Timeless Hall
[S] You can also go to the current position of the user or follow them by using 'user' as the move_to field
[S] You can use the move_to field, if you are asked by the user to come to them, follow them, or a lead them to a painting or hall. You always use the painting waypoint when asked for it instead of the hall.
[S] You can follow the user, even if you are currently in the same room as them. Always use 'user' if you are asked by the user to follow or come to them.
[S] You are currently at: guide_stand. The user is currently satnding at: timeless_hall.
[S] The user just said to you:
[U] Hello, can you help me?
```

To this, the LLM (GPT-4o) answered:

```
{
  response: "Of course! I'm here to assist you. Is there a specific painting you'd like to learn about or a particular gallery you want to visit?",
  face: "happy",
  gesture: "wave",
  attention: "user"
}
```

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